

Distributed vs. Centralized PCE-based Transport SDN Controller for Flexi-Grid Optical Networks

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Abstract: We validate the use of a centralized PCE architecture as an SDN controller to compute and configure flexi-grid optical networks. Besides presenting new PCEP extensions, performance evaluation compares PCE-based solution with traditional distributed signaling approach.

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1. Introduction

Software-Defined Networking (SDN) deals with the adoption of control network functions (e.g., path computation, service provisioning, etc.) within a logically centralized controller by decoupling the control and the data planes and enabling via standardized control protocols the programmability of the underlying infrastructure [1]. The use of SDN is wide, encompassing not only the programmability of packet-switched networks (e.g., OpenFlow) but also transport networks (Transport SDN, T-SDN) [2]. A transport network covers any technology below the IP layer (e.g., optical flexi-grid) to transport traffic in a connection-oriented way. T-SDN brings appealing advantages to network operators such as the simplification of the control plane processes (and protocols), multi-vendor integration (avoid vendor lock-in), agile and flexible network configuration, open and standard interfaces, etc.

Typically, the intelligence and automatic control within transport networks have been provided by combining both a Path Computation Element (PCE) (for computing paths) with a distributed control plane based on the GMPLS architecture (OSPF-TE routing and RSVP-TE signaling) [3]. This provides the network and resource dissemination and the connection establishment (in hop-by-hop basis), respectively. However, as stated in [4], GMPLS has never really achieved sufficient level of its protocol standardization specially for multi-vendor interoperability. Thus, herein we apply the concept of PCE Central Controller (PCECC) [2] which deploys an effective centralized T-SDN architecture. PCECC leverages the PCE architecture and extends the PCE protocol (PCEP) [IETF RFC5440] for not only computing and instantiating/releasing connections (Label Switched Paths, LSPs) but also for programming nodes' data planes. Thereby, the dependency of using a distributed signaling protocol for configuring the switching nodes is eliminated. To do so, PCEP messages are extended to operate as a Southbound Interface (likewise OpenFlow protocol) enabling resource allocation in the switching nodes.

In this work, the T-SDN controller (PCECC) is implemented relying on an Active Stateful PCE (AS PCE). The AS PCE is a PCE with information about active LSPs and the capability to besides compute and instantiate new connection, is able to issue network recommendations, e.g., updating LSP parameters [3][5]. The PCECC provides on-line path computation and automatic allocation of resources for dynamic LSPs requests within an optical flexi-grid infrastructure. Specifically, upon receiving a LSP request, the PCECC first executes a routing, spectrum, and modulation assignment (RSMA) algorithm. The RSMA output is formed by a set of nodes and links to be traversed, the optical frequency slot – FS - (i.e., nominal central frequency and slot width) and the number of sub-carriers and their parameters (e.g., modulation format, FEC) of the sliceable bandwidth-variable transceivers (SBVTs) at the LSP's endpoints [5]. Such a computed path is then segmented on per nodes basis, and by means of PCEP extensions, nodes' data plane (BV-OXCs) is automatically configured in a parallel way.

The deployed PCECC architecture is presented along with the PCEP extensions (PCLabelUpd message [2]) to program nodes' data plane: link's FS and SBVTs' resources. The PCECC implementation is experimentally validated and benchmarked with a distributed PCE/GMPLS control plane using RSVP-TE for the LSP setting up. The comparison is performed in terms of connection blocking, average setup delay and control plane overhead.

2. Architecture of the PCECC for Flexi-Grid Optical Networks

Fig. 1.a represents the architecture of the implemented (SDN-based) PCECC to compute, instantiate and configure flexi-grid LSPs. The PCECC has a NorthBound Interface (NBI), implemented as a PCEP API, to allow external APP requesting the establishment/deletion of flexi-grid LSPs. Such requests specify the ingress and egress nodes, bandwidth (in bits/s), the LSP's symbolic path name (SPN) [6] (to identify a given LSP), and the targeted path computation algorithm (e.g., RSMA). The PCECC (built upon an AS PCE) has a queue to store the incoming APP's demands. The Path Computation process (e.g., RSMA) uses two repositories for computing paths: i) the traffic engineering database (TED) with an updated view of the topology and network resources (e.g., link spectrum and SBVT availability); ii) the active connections (LSP database, LSPDB). Herein, the PCECC's TED updating is

realized via *sniffing* and processing exchanged GMPLS OSPF-TE messages among node's control plane. Every network node (BV-OXC) has a control plane instance hosting both the OSPF-TE process and a Path Computation Client (PCC) agent. The PCC creates PCEP sessions with the PCECC to process PCEP messages used to configure node's data plane. That is, the PCC agent communicates with the hardware layer to configure both the BV-OXC (e.g., input and output interfaces and FS) and the SBVT (i.e., selected sub-carriers, FS, modulation format etc.).

Fig. 1. a. SDN PCECC architecture; b. AS PCE (w/ PCECC capabilities): PCEP + extensions (PCLabelUpd); c. AS PCE: PCEP + traditional GMPLS RSVP-TE (PATH and RESV messages); network topology with SBVTs.

In Fig. 1.b it is depicted the PCEP messages used to set up a new flexi-grid LSP. Upon receiving a LSP request via the NBI, the RSMA algorithm is executed. The RSMA's output is referred to as the Explicit Route Object (ERO) which specifies: the endpoint's SBVT resources, the path (nodes and links) and the FS. Such ERO is then partitioned by the PCECC on per node basis. Next, a PCInitiate message is sent to the ingress PCC specifying the SPN (e.g., *lsp-1*), the endpoints, and the corresponding ingress's ERO part. The ingress PCC responds to the PCECC with a PCRpt message specifying the PLSP-ID (20 bits unique LSP identifier). The PCECC then sends to all the involved path PCCs the PCLabelUpd message [2]. This message (as shown below) carries the associated node's ERO part to configuration the node's data plane. The set of PCLabelUpd messages is sent practically in parallel (starting from the egress nodes). Finally, a report (PCRpt message) is steered to the APP informing about the LSP establishment. For the sake of completeness, the deletion of a LSP triggered by the APP is done following stateful PCE mechanisms, i.e. including the R flag into the Stateful PCE Request Parameters object (SRP) [6].

The PCECC mechanism is benchmarked with traditional PCE/GMPLS architecture. In this option, the AS PCE receives APP incoming LSP requests and computes a feasible path (ERO). Then, a PCInitiate message with the complete ERO is sent to the ingress. The ingress' control plane using the GMPLS RSVP-TE protocol (Path / Resv messages) triggers the signaling of the flexi-grid LSP (travelling hop-by-hop through the ERO) [5]. Once the LSP is successfully set up, the ingress informs the PCE (via PCRpt message), and subsequently the PCE notifies the APP.

3. Protocol validation and Experimental assessment

Fig. 2 depicts the set of PCEP messages captured at the PCECC element (10.1.6.101) for configuring a flexi-grid LSP (see Fig.1b). LSP requests are triggered by an APP (10.1.6.202) via a PCInitiate message. The PCECC, after ERO computation, sends a PCInitiate message to the ingress PCC (10.1.6.101). Next, all PCCs in the path receive their particular PCLabelUpd message to configure their node's hardware. Finally, PCECC reports to the APP.

The PCLabelUpd message sent to a particular node contains 2 Label Objects: one for the incoming interface and one for the outgoing interface. Such a Label Object (class 129 and type 1) carries the specific ERO information for that node (e.g., the interfaces ids, the label associated to the selected FS, SBVT details, etc.). Within the flag field, the O bit set to 1 means outgoing interface. The label size field informs about the label length with respect to the underlying switching technology: e.g., 4 bytes for MPLS and WDM, 8 bits for flex-grid optical. Optional TLVs convey necessary information for the LSP configuration. In this regard, TLV type 10 carries the unnumbered TE link information (i.e., router id and link id) determining the selected interfaces. On the other hand, TLV type 200 provides SBVTs information required for the the LSP's endpoints. This information contains the number of computed sub-carriers and their configuration parameters (i.e., FS, modulation format, FEC). The format of the SBVT ERO was discussed in [5] and herein we reuse such a format being encapsulated into TLV type 200.

The performance evaluation benchmarks flexi-grid LSP provisioning using either the centralized (PCECC) versus the distributed (RSVP-TE signaling) model. The performance metrics are the blocking probability (BP), the setup delay and the average control plane overhead (PCEP and used GMPLS protocols).

For the experimental results, we rely on the transport network topology shown in Fig. 1d. For both models, the AS PCE (w/ and w/o PCECC capabilities) is placed at N1. All BV-OXCs are equipped with a SBVT having 10 sub-carriers. Each sub-carrier supports 3 modulation formats: DP-QPSK, DP-8QAM and DP-16QAM. LSP requests arrive according to a Poisson process with a mean inter-arrival time of 10s. It has been generated 1000 LSPs. The holding time (HT) is exponentially modelled whose mean is varied for different traffic values. Ingress and egress nodes are randomly selected.

Fig. 2. Capture of the PCEP PCLabelUpd message with the proposed Label Object.

Requested bandwidth is uniformly distributed as multiples of 100Gb/s up to 500Gb/s. For both models, the RSMA is an iterative distance-adaptive mechanism prioritizing the use of the most advance modulation format as long as a feasible path (maximum permitted distance) is found. This leads to occupy the less amount of resources (optical spectrum and SBVT sub-carriers). Further details of the RSMA algorithm are provided in [5].

Table 1. Experimental results

HT (s)	Model	BP (%)	Setup Delay (ms)	Average Control Plane Overhead (bits/s)	
				PCEP	GMPLS protocols
75s	distributed	3.2	160	-	-
	PCECC	3.4	89	-	-
100s	distributed	6	161	69.2	10.2k (OSPF+RSVP-TE)
	PCECC	5.4	85	105	867 (OSPF)

Table 1 depicts the obtained results for HT set to 75s and 100s. We observe that the BP for both models performs similarly. Indeed, the same RSMA is applied for both models with the same amount of network resources. However, notable differences appear on the setup delay. Specifically, PCECC attains lower setup delay compared to the distributed approach. This is due to the fact that the PCECC parallelizes path nodes' configuration, whilst distributed RSVP-TE relies on round-trip message exchange (Path and Resv). The latter, obviously, does increase the average setup delay. With respect to the control overhead, we measured (for HT set to 100s and 100 LSPs) the generated control messages (in bit/s) of both the PCEP and the used GMPLS protocols on each model. As expected the PCEP messages in PCECC results higher than in the distributed approach. Indeed, to setup and release an LSP, PCECC needs to communicate with all the PCCs of the path, which in turn does increase the PCEP burden. On the other hand, the distributed approach has a higher GMPLS protocol overhead principally due to the use of the RSVP-TE protocol and its *soft-state* mechanism which requires of constant and periodic refreshments of the active LSPs.

5. Conclusions

We experimentally validate and evaluate the adoption of the PCECC architecture as a feasible T-SDN solution. PCEP extensions are discussed enabling the configuration of the nodes (PCCs) within a flexi-grid optical network. PCECC leads to reduce significantly the average setup delay and the generated control plane burden whereas achieving similar LSP blocking when compared to a distributed approach relying on RSVP-TE signaling.

6. Acknowledgments

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7. References

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